

Longitudinal metabolic profiling of obesity, gestational diabetes and hypertensive pregnancy disorders

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ON-LINE SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplemental figure 1. Mean differences (pooled mean across the three consecutive measurement points) of metabolic measures during pregnancy in PREDO study in the subgroup of women randomized to receive aspirin or placebo in comparison to women not in the trial. Dots refer to mean differences in the metabolic measures in SD units and error bars to their 99.8% Confidence Intervals (CI) between women randomized to receive aspirin (black) and not in the trial and between women randomized to receive placebo (gray) and not in the trial. The associations were adjusted for gestational week at the time of blood sampling and maternal age.

Supplemental figure 2. Mean differences (pooled mean across the three consecutive measurement points) of metabolic measures during pregnancy in RADIEL study in women receiving advice on diet and physical activity in comparison to women in the control group receiving standard care. Dots refer to mean differences in the metabolic measures in SD units and error bars to their 99.8% Confidence Intervals (CI). The associations were adjusted for gestational week at the time of blood sampling and maternal age.

Supplemental figure 3. Unadjusted mean differences (pooled mean across the three consecutive measurement points) of 225 metabolic measures during pregnancy between women with prepregnancy overweight or obesity in comparison to women with normal weight. Dots refer to mean differences in the metabolic measures in SD units and error bars to their 99.8% Confidence Intervals (CI) between overweight (blue color) and normal weight women and between obese (yellow color) and normal weight women.

Supplemental figure 4. Unadjusted mean differences (pooled mean across the three consecutive measurement points) of 225 metabolic measures during pregnancy between women with gestational diabetes in comparison to normoglycemic women. Dots refer to mean differences in the metabolic measures in SD units and error bars to their 99.8% Confidence Intervals (CI).

Supplemental figure 5. Unadjusted mean differences (pooled mean across the three consecutive measurement points) of 225 metabolic measures during pregnancy between women with hypertensive disorder in comparison to normoglycemic women. Dots refer to mean differences in the metabolic measures in SD units and error bars to their 99.8% Confidence Intervals (CI) between women with preeclampsia (yellow) and normotensive women; women with chronic hypertension (blue) and normotensive women; and women with gestational hypertension (brown) and normotensive women.

Supplemental figure 6. Trajectories of changes in 68 metabolic measures in three consecutive measurement points during pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

Supplemental figure 7. Trajectories of changes in 68 metabolic measures in three consecutive measurement points during pregnancy in women with and without gestational diabetes.

Supplemental figure 8. Mean differences (pooled mean across the three consecutive measurement points) and mean differences in the change (mean change across the three consecutive measurement points; right panel) of metabolic measures during

pregnancy between women with gestational diabetes (GDM) treated with diet or insulin in comparison to normoglycemic women. Dots refer to mean differences in the metabolic measures in SD units and error bars to their 99.8% Confidence Intervals (CI) between women with diet-treated GDM (gray) and normoglycemic women, and between women with insulin-treated GDM (black) and normoglycemic women. In the analyses of mean differences (main effect models) the associations were adjusted for gestational week at the time of blood sampling, cohort and maternal age and the analyses of change (interaction models) additionally for the main effects of GDM (model 1; dots and bars); further adjustments included parity, education, substance use during pregnancy and BMI (Model 4; significance indicated with dGDM for diet-treated and iGDM for insulin-treated GDM).

Supplemental figure 9. Trajectories of changes in 68 metabolic measures in three consecutive measurement points during pregnancy in normotensive women and women with gestational hypertension, preeclampsia and chronic hypertension.

Supplemental figure 10. Mean differences (pooled mean across the three consecutive measurement points; left panel) and mean differences in the change (mean change across the three consecutive measurement points; right panel) of metabolic measures during pregnancy between women with gestational hypertension in comparison to normotensive women. Dots refer to mean differences and mean change per one pregnancy week in the metabolic measures in SD units and error bars to their 99.8% Confidence Intervals (CI). In the analyses of mean differences (main effect models) the associations were adjusted for gestational week at the time of blood sampling, cohort and maternal age and the analyses of change (interaction models) additionally for the main effects of gestational hypertension.

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|----------------------------|-------------------------------|--|------------------------------------|----------------------|-----------------------|--------------------------------|------------------------|----------------------|-----------------------|----------------------------|----------------------------|
| ● Chronic hypertension | 1. Amino acids | 5. Cholesterol | 9. Fluid balance | 13. Inflammation | 17. Large LDL | 21. Lipoprotein particle sizes | 25. Medium LDL ratios | 29. Small HDL | 33. Small VLDL | 37. Very large HDL ratios | 41. Very small VLDL ratios |
| ● Preeclampsia | 2. Apolipoproteins | 6. Chylomicrons and extremely large VLDL | 10. Glycolysis related metabolites | 14. Ketone bodies | 18. Large LDL ratios | 22. Medium HDL | 26. Medium VLDL | 30. Small HDL ratios | 34. Small VLDL ratios | 38. Very large VLDL | |
| ● Gestational hypertension | 3. Aromatic amino acids | 7. Fatty acid ratios | 11. IDL | 15. Large HDL | 19. Large VLDL | 23. Medium HDL ratios | 27. Medium VLDL ratios | 31. Small LDL | 35. Triglycerides | 39. Very large VLDL ratios | |
| | 4. Branched-chain amino acids | 8. Fatty acids | 12. IDL ratios | 16. Large HDL ratios | 20. Large VLDL ratios | 24. Medium LDL | 28. Other lipids | 32. Small LDL ratios | 36. Very large HDL | 40. Very small VLDL | |

Supplemental figure 6. Trajectories of changes in 68 metabolic measures in three consecutive measurement points during pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

Trajectories of changes in lipoprotein subclasses metabolites across pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

Trajectories of changes in lipoprotein particle sizes across pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

Trajectories of changes in cholesterol measures across pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

Trajectories of changes in glycerides and phospholipids across pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

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Trajectories of changes in apolipoproteins across pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

Trajectories of changes in fatty acids during pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

Trajectories of changes in fatty acids ratios during pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

Trajectories of changes in glycolysis related metabolites across pregnancy in normal weight, overweight and obese women.

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